

EFFECTIVENESS OF MARUNGKO APPROACH IN TEACHING READING

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Effectiveness of Marungko Approach in Teaching Reading

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Abstract

This study determined the effectiveness of Marungko Approach in teaching reading to grade two non-reader pupils of Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School, Katangawan District, General Santos City. It used an experimental design, specifically with-in group design where the same participants take part in each condition to determine the effectiveness of Marungko Approach. The researcher prepared self-made reading materials to be tested adopting the marungko approach in teaching reading. The reading materials were submitted for validation to its efficacy and its authenticity by the expert validators. Findings of the study revealed that majority of the grade 2 non-readers had very low scores during the pre-test and obtained high scores during the post-test after utilizing the Marungko approach. The results of the study showed that the use of Marungko approach in teaching reading was effective for grade 2 non-reader pupils. Furthermore, the result of the study could be the basis and reference for future research studies and would give confidence to expand understanding in the field of education and the advancement of the research process.

Keywords: *educational management, learners, marungko approach, non-reader, teaching reading, philippines*

Introduction

Reading promotes an individual's confidence in modern society. It enables people to act creatively and critically in an ever-changing and highly competitive world. Despite this valuable information concerning the relevant impact of reading literacy on a country's economic growth, many children worldwide are still labelled "not good enough" in their reading literacy classes. Poor reading performance could significantly affect all other learning areas in different subject areas (Bautista, 2019; Khalfaoui, 2018).

In this case, they need better foundational reading competencies in the beginning reading, such as identifying letter names, recognizing letter sounds, discriminating initial sounds, reading familiar words, and reading the oral passage. The failure to solidify these foundational reading skills at the beginning stage can create a ripple effect in the latter years of a child's quest to develop higher competencies in reading and, ultimately, in other aspects of life (Brink & Nel, 2019).

Consonant to this, the study was conducted to find a possible fitting solution through a teaching reading approach called Marungko that may help reading teachers unlock the keys to illiteracy in reading. The Marungko approach equips Grade One learners with the necessary reading skills to improve their reading achievement. In addition, guided by this reading approach, children are taught to know the letter sound of the Filipino alphabet (Repaso & Macalisang, 2024).

In the case of the Philippines, data shows through the Program for International Assessment (PISA) in 2019 that Filipino students aged 15 received a rating of 340 points in extensive reading, which was less than the average of 487 points, consequently making the Philippines the last among 79 countries. This fact requires Philippine educators to revisit the traces of developing reading comprehension skills for their learners down to the beginning reading stage (Abella, 2022; Boltron & Ramos, 2021).

Accordingly, as mandated by DepEd Memorandum 173, series of 2019, all offices at the Central Office (CO), Regional Offices (ROs), Schools Division Offices (SDOs), and school levels are strongly encouraged to respond to Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiative) by intensifying their reading advocacy to turn all learners into readers at their grade level and allowing teachers to become effective reading facilitators (Dorado & Medina, 2022).

That is why beginning reading is essential in grade one. Because of this, at the beginning of a task, in particular, teachers should plan and provide an effective reading program to improve and develop the reading competencies of their learners. Reading also influences student knowledge and understanding (De Belen, 2017; Smith et al., 2021).

Thus, along with this concept, teachers need to innovate and or adopt acceptable teaching reading approaches to cater to the needs of the learners in the process of learning, such as the development of the ability to identify letter names, identify letter sounds, discriminate initial sounds, read familiar words and read the oral passage in the beginning reading stage. Thus, regardless of a teacher's teaching approach, the same goal should always be in sight: to develop these foundational reading competencies so that the learner can become more productive later on.

Research Objectives

This study endeavoured to determine the effectiveness of the Marungko Approach in teaching reading for grade two non-reader pupils of Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School enrolled for the school year 2021-2022. Specifically, this study had the following objectives:

1. To determine the pre-test scores of Grade 2 non-reader pupils.

2. To ascertain the post-test scores of Grade 2 non-reader pupils.
3. To measure the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores.

Methodology

This section discusses the study's research design, locale, population and sample, research instruments, and data collection.

Research Design

This research used repeated measures design to investigate the effectiveness of the marungko approach in teaching reading to grade two non-reader pupils. The feature of this experimental design is that data is collected from the same sample unit under various conditions or at different periods. Moreover, individuals in all experiment conditions are members of the same group. To assess their efficacy, the same individuals participate in pre-and post-tests. Within-groups or within-subjects are additional terms for the repeated measures design (McLeod, 2017; Roopmok & Panishkan, 2020).

In a within-subjects design, every sample member receives the same treatments. Thus, the same participants are used as subjects, and an experiment is repeated under different treatments. The core goal is to measure changes over time or from other treatments for outcomes such as attitudes, learning, or performance. Also, the objective was to reanalyze the reported data and compare the findings to the original data (McLeod, 2017; White et al., 2019).

With this design, a single group was examined in this study through pre-test and post-test design as an intervention was applied regarding implementing the developed supplementary material. Through pre-and post-tests, the researchers gathered the information for the assessment of the progress of the pupils. The sequence of the marungko approach was given the same, so it was an accurate measure of the pupils' gains and failures during the post-test. The researcher is intended to determine the effectiveness of the marungko approach in teaching reading to grade two non-reader pupils (McLeod, 2017).

Participants

In this study, the research subjects were the grade two non-reader pupils of Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School enrolled in 2021-2022. They were the subject of the study because they had difficulty reading the given texts independently. They were identified through the help of their respective advisers, who hold their Pre-test PHIL-IRI results. Based on the pre-test result, out of 157 grade two learners, 42 pupils of these were categorized as non-readers were used as the study subjects.

The items was attested to their efficacy by expert validators and then pilot tested. Initially, the proponent made a 50-item Test instrument based on the second grading lesson. After formulating and completing the device draft, she piloted it to homogeneously answer the chosen 25 grade 2 non-readers from a neighbouring school. Other items that were marked revised or improved were carried out. Out of the 50-item Test, the researcher developed an official 25-item test used in the pre-test and post-test from supplementary reading materials.

Additionally, this study used the purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is an intentional selection of participants based on their capacity to elucidate a specific theme, concept, or phenomenon. The method of choosing a sample by selecting a subject based on a particular objective rather than the area's level is known as purposeful sampling (Casteel & Bridier, 2021).

A purposive sample is a non-probability sample chosen by the study's goals and the population's characteristics. It is also the one whose components are specified in a crucial way to the investigation. Convenience sampling is different from purposeful sampling. This type of non-probability sampling, sometimes called judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, involves researchers using their judgment to pick people from the population to participate in surveys (Andrade, 2021; Crossman, 2020).

Table 1. *Talaan ng Baitang sa Pagbabasa (Grade Reading Profile) Phil-Iri sa Filipino SY 2020-2021*

No.	Baitang at Pangkat	Enrollment	Nakuha ang Pagtatasa (Tested)	Pangkatasang Pagtatasa (Group Screening Test)	Antas ng Pagbasa (Reading Level)				
					Panimulang pagtatasa (Pre-Test)				
				>14	<14	Ind.	Ins.	Fruz	NR
1	2-Tamba	38	38	20	18	0	3	5	10
2	2-Eria	41	41	20	21	4	2	3	12
3	2-Reyes	38	38	14	24	0	6	5	13
4	2-Gumaga	40	40	13	27	5	7	8	7
	<i>Kabuuan</i>	157	157	67	90	9	18	21	42

Instruments

There were two instruments that the researcher used to gather the data

needed. First was the pre-test and post-test questionnaire, composed of 25 questions the researcher initially made. The second instrument was the self-made supplementary reading materials given to the non-reader pupils after the pre-test.

The researcher created supplementary reading materials following the marungko approach. The first to be given was the reading material composing different letter sounds, which the learners could identify through pictures. Next to be delivered were the reading materials comprising consonant-vowel, which can be read through syllabifying. Then, read different phrases with the words at, say, mga, and ng. After that, they read sentences.

Lastly, they read a story and answered questions. The results in the pre-test and post-test were the basis for determining the effectiveness of the mango approach in teaching reading. The researcher administered the tool to the four groups of non-reader pupils individually to ensure proper implementation.

Data Collection

At first, the researcher developed reading materials following the style of the mango approach. It has five lessons which were Aralin 1- Pagkilala Ng Tunog Ng Letra Gamit Ang Larawan, Aralin 2- Pagsasama-Sama Ng Katinig At Patinig, Aralin 3- Pagbabasa Ng Parirala Na May Ang, At, Ay, Mga, At Ng, Aralin 4- Pagbabasa Ng Pangungusap, and Aralin 5- Pagbabasa Ng Talata At Nakasagot Sa Tanong. The items on the pre-and post-tests were designed with the idea that they should be found in the additional reading resources. The investigator then created a lesson plan to determine the best teaching strategy. Next, to support the claim that the reading materials were developed independently, the researcher made a letter of authenticity verified by knowledgeable validators. Before being put through a pilot test, the items' effectiveness was additionally confirmed by qualified validators. We completed the other items that were identified as improved or updated. From the 50-item test, the researcher created an official 25-item test used in the post-test and pre-test using additional reading resources.

Next, the researcher asked permission from the Graduate School Office after validating the research instruments. And, then to the General Santos City Division Office to introduce the research study. Next, she went to the Katangawan District to allow the research to be carried out at Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School. Finally, the researcher asked permission from the School Principal to conduct the study on four Grade 2 sections. The PHIL-IRI coordinator was also asked for permission to obtain the reading inventory of grade 2 pupils. To identify the non-readers, the teachers used the pre-test Phil-IRI, an oral test given to learners to measure reading ability.

The pre-test and post-test questionnaires were individually given to the subjects with the proper guidance of the researcher. The results of the learners' answers were described as 5- Very High, 4- High, 3- Average, 2- Low, and 1- Very Low.

Statistical Tool

The data obtained from the survey questionnaire were analyzed and treated using the frequency count, percentage, and T-test. The experimentation mechanics involved several vital steps. Firstly, a suitable sample of participants, such as learners from a specific grade level or educational setting, was selected. Then, a control group and experimental group were established, with the control group receiving the traditional approach in teaching reading and the experimental group using the Marungko approach. A pre-test was conducted to assess both groups' initial knowledge or skills. The experimental group engaged with the Marungko approach, while the control group followed the traditional approach. A post-test was administered after three months to measure the reading skills of both groups. The test results were gathered to determine how successful the Marungko approach is at teaching reading, and statistical techniques were applied to the data.

Additionally, the pre-and post-test results were calculated using a frequency count. It was a matter of calculating the instances in which the grade 2 students' pre-and post-test results occurred. Frequency statistics, like the results of the grade 2 students' pre-and post-test scores, count the instances of each variable (Mishra et al., 2019).

Moreover, the percentage was used to determine the rate of the scores obtained from the pre-and post-tests and to get the average of the pre-test and post-test. The data was presented in tabular form to facilitate interpretation and analysis.

Lastly, the T-test was used to calculate the significant difference between the obtained scores in the pre-test and the post-test of the grade 2 pupils.

Results

This section presents the results of the data gathered. Hence, the tabular presentations and discussions were organized based on each problem, as in Chapter 1 of the study.

3.1 Pre-test Score of Grade 2 learners in Reading before utilizing Marungko Approach

Table 2 presents the pre-test score of Grade Two pupils in the marungko approach before the treatment was given.

None of the 42 students received an average, high, or very high score, while 8 (or 19%) had low scores in reading, and 34 (or 81%) had very low scores in reading. Most grade two students were sluggish in reading before the mango approach was applied, as shown in the table. Generally, the mean of the 30 pupils for the pre-test is 26.4 or 52 percent, which is described as very low.

In addition, Marungko Approach and phonics were used at De Los Santos Community School in Marungko, Angat, Bulacan,

Philippines, Two teachers from there first introduced. The "Mastery of Sounds of Letters" technique teach youngsters the letter sounds of the Filipino alphabet as their first knowledge. For this approach, instead of teaching alphabetic letter names, teachers teach letter sounds. When used in reading teaching, scaffolding does not entail giving pupils the solution, performing their work, providing suggestions, or simplifying and learning the material (De Belen, 2017; Rubin & Traverro, 2022).

Table 2. *Frequency Counts and Percentage Distribution of Pre-Test Sources of Grade Two Pupils Before Utilizing Morungko*

<i>Number of Pupils</i>	<i>Pre-Test Scores</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	2	8	Very Low
2	4	16	Very Low
3	2	8	Very Low
4	6	24	Low
5	3	12	Very Low
6	2	8	Very Low
7	10	40	Low
8	5	20	Very Low
9	8	32	Low
10	4	16	Very Low
11	3	12	Very Low
12	1	4	Very Low
13	2	5	Very Low
14	1	4	Very Low
15	2	8	Very Low
16	2	8	Very Low
17	3	12	Very Low
18	5	20	Very Low
19	2	8	Very Low
20	9	36	Loq
21	4	16	Very Low
22	9	36	Low
23	2	8	Very Low
24	3	12	Very Low
25	5	20	Very Low
26	2	8	Very Low
27	3	12	Very Low
28	4	16	Very Low
29	2	8	Very Low
30	5	20	Very Low
31	10	40	Low
31	5	20	Very Low
32	5	20	Very Low
33	5	20	Very Low
34	7	28	Low
35	5	20	Very Low
36	3	12	Very Low
37	2	8	Very Low
38	8	32	Low
39	2	8	Very Low
40	5	20	Very Low
41	2	8	Very Low
42	5	20	Very Low
Mean	174	15	Very Low

3.2 Post-test Score of Grade 2 Pupils after utilizing Marungko approach

The post-test results of grade 2 students who used the marungko technique are shown in Table 3. The data were treated using frequency counts and percentage distributions.

Table 3 shows the improvement in scores as compared to the pre-test.

It was shown that 4 or 10% of the students had very high scores. There were 15, or 36%, with a high score; 22, or 52%, with an average score; and 1, or 2%, with a low score. In the post-test, all of the students had a manageable score. The post-test mean score of 15.19 demonstrated a mean score improvement from 4.14. Detailed information from the learners' post-test can be found in Appendix F. Generally, the mean scores of the post-test of 30 pupils were 37. 63 or 75. Twenty-six percent describe it as average. The Marungko Approach is evaluated as an effective reading strategy for teaching reading skills at Maranao Elementary School in San Manuel Isabela

(Goyja, 2023).

It has been found that the Marungko Approach is a helpful strategy for improving students' early reading proficiency. It builds on the development of additional reading micro-competencies and, eventually, strengthens and enhances reading comprehension skills, which are critical at higher education levels (Boltron & Ramos, 2021).

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Post-Test Scores of Grade Two Pupils after utilizing Marungko approach*

<i>Number of Pupils</i>	<i>Post-Test Scores</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	13	52	Average
2	16	66	High
3	11	44	Average
4	14	56	Average
5	12	45	Average
6	11	44	Average
7	22	55	Very High
8	13	52	Average
9	20	50	High
10	11	44	Average
11	14	56	Average
12	10	40	Low
13	13	52	Average
14	11	44	Average
15	16	64	High
16	13	52	Average
17	15	60	Average
18	16	64	High
19	11	44	Average
20	21	54	Very High
21	16	64	High
22	20	50	High
23	14	56	Average
24	13	52	Average
25	18	72	High
26	11	44	Average
27	15	60	Average
28	14	56	Average
29	12	43	Average
30	17	68	High
31	22	55	Very High
32	18	72	High
33	15	60	Average
34	19	76	High
35	17	65	High
36	17	65	High
37	12	45	Average
38	21	54	Very High
39	16	64	High
40	17	65	High
41	13	52	Average
42	18	72	High
Mean	638	60.76	Average

Table 4 showed the effectiveness of supplementary material utilizing the Marungko approach in teaching reading among grade two non-readers. The t-test with uncorrelated data was used since the population was large. The data revealed that the computed t-value was 26.49, more significant than the tabular value of 1.645; this led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Furthermore, it means that using supplementary material utilizing the Marungko approach effectively improved the reading performance of grade 2 non-readers. Also, the first-grade Thai students' English reading comprehension and performance were examined to determine the impact of the Marungko Approach. It was shown that teaching phonics improved students' reading comprehension compared to not teaching phonics (Yayen, 2018).

Table 4. *Effectiveness of Supplementary Materials utilizing Marungko approach in Teaching Reading among Grade 2 non-readers*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>T Value</i>		<i>Description</i>	<i>Decision</i>
		<i>Computed</i>	<i>Tabular</i>		<i>a=0.05</i>
Pre-test	n-1	24.49	1.645	Significant	Reject Ho

Score versus	41
Post-test Score	

Discussion

This section presents the discussion, conclusion, and recommendations from the findings that surfaced from the data analysis. This repeated measures study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of the marungko approach in teaching reading to grade two non-reader pupils of Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School, General Santos City.

This research utilized the repeated measures designed to comprehensively examine the effectiveness of the marungko approach in teaching reading to the grade two non-reader pupils of Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School, Katangawan District, Division of General Santos City. This study involved 42 pupils whose respective advisers identified them as non-readers using the Phil-Iri Assessment.

According to the current study's findings, the Marungko Approach was among the best strategies for teaching beginning reading. Instructors are urged to implement this strategy for students in Grade 1 and those struggling with reading in other grade levels. This approach is beneficial for beginning readers. Given that the study revealed improved student reading skills, the instructor may employ the Marungko Approach in distance learning if the parents and teachers properly monitor the students (Guevarra, 2022).

Thus, the present study underscores the need for school administrators to find ways to widen the program to help every learner and teacher teach reading skills using the Marungko Approach and extend support for improving and developing the reading skills of their pupils. Additionally, pupils who are involved as well as those not directly involved, would gain benefits because this study could help them to improve their level of 4.1 reading skill and allow them to know the different ways to enhance their reading ability.

Conclusion

Based on the data gathered, it is concluded that most grade 2 learners had shallow scores during the pre-test before utilizing the Marungko approach. Also, most grade 2 learners had high scores during the post-test after using the Marungko approach. Lastly, the Marungko approach in teaching reading effectively improved the reading performance of grade 2 non-readers.

Based on the conclusion, it is recommended that the School Administrators set aside funds to create additional materials to duplicate the lessons required for teaching the Marungko method and widen the program to help every learner learn reading skills using the Marungko Approach. Similarly, the principal may conduct INSET related to the integration of the Marungko Approach to improve and develop the reading skills of the learners and may closely monitor the teacher's performance on the integration of the Marungko Approach to support and test the effectiveness of the strategies vis-a-vis the reading performance of the pupils.

Additionally, teachers are urged to participate in training and may integrate and practice using the Marungko Approach in teaching reading. Also, parents may be taught the Marungko technique to teach their non-reader children at home during this pandemic. Pupils may also be given attention and given different reading materials to motivate them to practice their reading ability.

Furthermore, the researcher suggests that educators create reading programs and activities that cater to students who struggle with reading and give parents a list of YouTube links linked to reading to their children and use the Marungko Approach as an early reading instruction and intervention for learners. In addition, the researcher gives the authority to future researchers to conduct a proper experimental design where functional and control groups are undertaken to assess the method's effectiveness over other forms of teaching reading. Related research may focus on teaching the Marungko approach to non-reader elementary kids.

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